

APPLICATION OF MECHANISMS OF PROBLEM-ORIENTED LEARNING IN THE TEACHING OF PHARMACOLOGY AND PHARMACOTHERAPY AT THE FACULTIES OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY**Filipets N.,***Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
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Chair of Pharmacy***ABSTRACT**

Higher medical and pharmaceutical education today is impossible without a combination of highlighting the time-tested basic principles that have become dogma within the academic disciplines, and modern achievements of fundamental science and practice. To a large extent, this concerns the teaching of pharmacology, clinical pharmacology, clinical pharmacy and pharmacotherapeutic aspects of clinical disciplines. Difficulties in teaching are due to the large amount of educational material, its dynamic replenishment with new scientific information about medicinal products, as well as changes in treatment recommendations. In general, the solution to such a problem largely depends on teaching skills. Avoiding the routine sameness of education, balanced opposition to traditional methods of new pedagogical approaches is a natural modern process. The structural components of professional competence are motivational, cognitive, personal, communicative, control-reflective components, which are formed, in particular, thanks to problem-oriented learning. Problem-oriented learning adapts medical students and pharmacists to real problems that will arise in future practical activities. Thanks to this approach, the goal is achieved resulting in formation of a competent, competitive specialist whose knowledge and skills are relevant at the time of graduation for obtaining higher education.

Keywords: problem-oriented learning, higher education, pharmacology, pharmacotherapy.

The dynamic development of pharmacology is evidenced by a wide range of drugs on the world pharmaceutical market, which is continuously supplemented with new names thanks to innovative medical technologies. It should be noted that along with new discoveries, there is an expansion of pharmacodynamics, therefore, of approved indications for existing, well-known drugs. Corresponding changes are taking place in recommendations for drug treatment and graduates' competencies. For the effective teaching of pharmacology and pharmacotherapy of diseases, the teacher must consider the thematic material in such a way that, together with fundamental ideas, students can determine the advantages of drugs, taking into account new information about pharmacological characteristics and recommendations for pharmacotherapy when analyzing individual clinical situations.

It is worth noting that new teaching methods are components of the transformation of higher education. Therefore, the question of compliance of the teaching methods developed by the department and the implemented pedagogical innovations to the requirements for the step-by-step effective formation of a modern competent medical and pharmaceutical specialist is relevant.

The aim of the work is to focus attention on methodical approaches to teaching pharmacology and pharmacotherapy, in particular, on the mechanisms of problem-oriented learning, for medical students and

pharmacists to improve the efficiency of the process of acquiring the necessary competencies for further educational and practical activities.

Methodology. The work uses a descriptive method that highlights the mechanisms and advantages of problem-oriented learning.

The difficulties of teaching pharmacology and pharmacotherapy are caused, on the one hand, by the content – a large volume of educational material and its dynamic replenishment and at the expense of obtaining new scientific information, as well as changes in treatment recommendations. On the other hand – with teaching and learning [1].

The ability of a doctor with sufficient standardized knowledge and competence to adapt to the situation based on basic experience is today defined as creative potential [2]. In the field of medical and pharmaceutical education, the growth of creative potential makes it impossible to follow only traditional teaching methods. Today, in addition to the skills inherent in the profession, employers pay attention to soft skills, which help to perform work effectively, develop a business and successfully build a future career. Such personal qualities as team work skills, communication skills, orientation to results are achieved at the stages of obtaining higher education thanks to new pedagogical technologies, their formation depends on the professional competence of the teacher. Mastering and putting into practice new pedagogical approaches is an increase in one's

own pedagogical skills, a desire for self-education, development of one's own potential and self-realization, and, ultimately, a guarantee of professional burnout of a teacher.

One of the main tasks of education when covering the issues of pharmacology and pharmacotherapy is encouraging students to realize the professional and cognitive need for this knowledge, which is also a factor in the formation of their professional identity [3]. Today, guided by unified medical care protocols, a qualified specialist prefers pathogenetic treatment. Determining the mechanisms of the effect of drugs that correct the disorders in the body that arose against the background of the disease is not possible without knowledge of physiology, pathological physiology, biochemistry, microbiology, etc. This approach provides interdisciplinary integration [4], since not only drugs are included in various educational programs in many courses, but also the analysis of pharmacodynamics involves knowledge acquired in other departments. Problem-oriented learning, which eliminates the limitations of passive learning, is impossible without interdisciplinary integration. Problem-based learning is a student-centered method in which complex real-world problems are used to stimulate thinking and problem-solving abilities in the teaching and learning process [5].

The mechanism of problem-oriented learning is work in groups, where the problem is identified step by step, ideas and knowledge are generated, the necessary information is summarized and analyzed, erroneous thoughts and solutions are filtered out, the knowledge obtained is synthesized and applied to solve the problem situation [6]. The use of situational tasks in the teaching of pharmacology and pharmacotherapy remains an effective tool for dialogue with individual students and the involvement of all those present to participate in the discussed problems with justification of the correct answer. With this in mind, when forming training groups and assigning roles, attention is focused not only on choosing a drug that is adequate for the clinical situation. In this case, information on rational pharmacotherapy, when it is advisable to give preference to a certain drug, against other synergistic in action, is a mandatory component of training. Therefore, the tasks for the groups may differ and consist in determining a number of treatment drugs; preferences of individual representatives; demonstrably effective. In fact, a group of students can use Internet services to check the effectiveness of prescribed drugs. Taking into account the existing functional and metabolic continuum, as well as the generally recognized syndromes of combined damage to organs and systems, it is advisable for another group of students to choose drugs with multi-organ therapeutic effects. It emphasizes the principles of combined pharmacotherapy and the advantages of drugs with fixed doses. A separate group of students focuses on side effects, their treatment and prevention, so that students understand that there is no drug that is not associated with risk, as well as the need for a balanced, individual approach to pharmacotherapy [7]. At the same time, a group of students highlights the ethical aspects of prescribing or dispensing drugs. It is important to focus on medication errors and their causes, which

are related to taking medications – prescribing, dispensing, storing, dosing, using, ignoring safety precautions. Also emphasize the ethical issues of drug advertising: what is allowed / prohibited by law; when non-compliance with drug advertising results in life-threatening consequences of self-treatment.

The results of such training are the ability of students, according to the distribution of roles, to conduct an independent search in sources of scientific information, to accumulate new knowledge and to apply it to solve the problem. At the final stage of the lesson, thanks to the analysis of everyone's contribution to the joint work, including the students themselves, it is easier to adequately determine personal effectiveness and evaluate everyone.

It is worth noting once again that the formation of clinical thinking largely depends on the ability to convey to the student the need to integrate the knowledge acquired in other departments, while at the same time worrying about the integration of theory and practice at further stages of education, in order to obtain higher competence in the interests of healthcare workers, as well as patients and consumers of pharmaceutical products. A competent workforce is one, if not the central, goal of education. However, no specialist can be equally competent in all areas of health care [8]. At the same time, communicative competence, as one of the main competences of all health care workers, is the key to success in practical activities.

In problem-oriented learning, the process of synthesis and application of new knowledge forms the student's ability to perform tasks together with other people within the limits of the assigned task, that is, communication skills are modulated. Students exchange opinions at the beginning and information accumulated during the class, sift out false statements and together make a decision on a problematic situation.

So, with the help of problem-oriented learning, students' communication skills are improved more effectively than with the help of traditional methods, which are individual questions or individual control tasks. Communication skills are necessary not only for interaction between a patient and a doctor or a pharmacist and a visitor to a pharmacy. Professional communication is a process of exchanging thoughts, ideas, and information that leads to mutual understanding. The ability to communicate and understand interlocutors, convey your vision and achieve your goal through communication is formed gradually and over time. Medical and pharmaceutical professionals may not be able to communicate effectively if they are not confident in their knowledge. Therefore, problem-oriented learning is a tool for teaching communication skills through the prism of acquired knowledge necessary for professional communication.

It should be emphasized that the indisputable advantages of problem-oriented learning are the involvement of all students in solving a common problem, in this context – the selection and justification of the effectiveness and safety of pharmacotherapy, which excludes evaluation only for the coverage of a separate issue of the lesson (regarding classification, pathogenetic aspects of pharmacotherapy, selection of routes of

administration, dosage, prescribing). In turn, the teacher, in addition to focusing on the content of the subject and identifying gaps in knowledge, makes a conclusion for himself about the personal characteristics of the students. Taking into account the individual characteristics and different needs of students, relationships are modeled, giving priority to partnership. The student is perceived as a whole personality, which, together with integrated learning, also corresponds to the content of the holistic direction in education [9].

The stages and mechanisms of problem-oriented learning, connected by problem situations, involve feedback and reflection. Reflection is one of the necessary components of medical education [10]. Students work together to confront the problem. The justification of approaches to pharmacotherapy is based on the understanding of physiological, pathogenetic aspects, general and special pharmacology, medical prescription, etc. In the conditions of teamwork, there is an opportunity to show knowledge of various academic disciplines, assess one's own capabilities, realize shortcomings, and feel the shift and progress in education. The reflective ability of students reflects their critical ability, because it helps students to quickly perform an educational task, to act as an expert in their own educational activity and to check the obtained results and make an independent assessment. Therefore, the choice of problem-oriented teaching methods is an effective lever in the formation and strengthening of critical thinking and learning motivation.

So, today the volume of information has significantly increased, and, in accordance with the requirements for the effectiveness of teaching pharmacology and pharmacotherapy, and the ability to treat largely depends on the acquired knowledge in the future. Problem-oriented learning, which in its essence is a constructivist theoretical perspective [11], is an effective pedagogical method for students to acquire knowledge, obtain new information, develop communication skills, and make vital decisions.

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